

Selective complexometric determination of mercury using 4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole as masking reagent

K. Subrahmanya Bhat, B. Narayana*, C. H. R. Nambiar and B. Ramachandra

Department of Studies in Chemistry, Mangalore University, Mangalagangotri-574 199, India

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Mercury and other ions are complexed with an excess of EDTA and the excess EDTA is titrated with ZnSO₄ solution at pH 5.0–6.0 using xylenol orange as indicator. An excess of alcoholic solution of 4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole is then added to decompose the Hg-EDTA complex and the released EDTA is titrated with standard ZnSO₄ solution. Accurate results have been obtained for 1.86–74.46 mg of mercury with relative error of <0.39 and standard deviation <0.04 mg. The method has been successfully applied for the analysis of Hg in synthetic alloy solutions.

Mercury is usually determined in presence of associated cations by the selective decomposition of relatively weak Hg-EDTA complex with masking agents such as thiosemicarbazide¹, thiourea² and *N*-allylthiourea³, and the liberated EDTA is titrated using standard metal ion solutions. Interference by copper is severe in these cases. Potassium iodide⁴ is used as a masking for the determination of Hg^{II} in the presence of Cu^{II} in alkaline medium, but several cations interfere. 4-Amino-5-mercapto-3-*n*-propyl-1,2,4-triazole⁵, 2-imidazolidenethione⁶, hexahydropyrimidine-2-thione⁷, thiocyanate⁸, sodium nitrite⁹ and acetyl acetone¹⁰ are also used as masking agents for the determination of Hg^{II}. These reagents are convenient but some require tedious and time-consuming preparations^{5–7}. Even though 2-mercaptoethanol¹¹ is a good masking agent it is unpleasant to use because of its smell. Sodium sulphite¹² is also a reagent for mercury, but interference by Tl^{III} and Pd^{II} is avoided only by using secondary masking agents.

In the present communication, 4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole has been used as masking agent for the indirect complexometric determination of Hg^{II}.

Results and Discussion

Hg^{II} forms a stable water-soluble complex with 4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole. The sensitivity of the method is established by the effect of various quantities of 1% 4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole in alcohol used for the recovery of 9.31 mg of Hg^{II}. Also 3 ml of 1% reagent is required for the recovery of 9.31 mg of Hg^{II}.

Results for Hg^{II} determination in mercuric nitrate solution have relative errors of <0.39% and standard deviation <0.4%. An excess of the reagent had no adverse effect and the absence of any precipitate in the reaction mixture favours a sharp end-point. Hence, the titration is quantitative and precise.

The effect of different cations, anions and few water-

soluble organic substances on the quantitative determination of Hg^{II} was investigated with 9.31 mg of Hg^{II} in solution. No interference was observed when following ions and organic substances were present: 25 mg of Cd^{II}, Pb^{II}, V^{IV}, Ca^{II}, F⁻, Cl⁻, NO₃⁻ or Br⁻; 30 mg of Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Mg^{II}, Tl^{III}, or In^{III}; 20 mg of W^{VI}, Ag^I; 50 mg of La^{III}, Ce^{III} or Dy^{III}; 60 mg of benzaldehyde, phenol, carbonylhydrazide, aniline, acetone or *p*-chlorophenol. Sn^{IV}, Ni^{II}, Zr^{IV} and Ti^{IV} interfered severely. The interference can be obviated using suitable secondary masking agents. Relative errors in the above interference did not exceed +0.21%.

Artificial mixtures of Mg, Sn and Na with Hg^{II} were prepared, and analysed using the proposed method. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Determination of Hg^{II} in artificial mixtures*

Mixture	Metal ion composition %	Hg found* %	Rel. std. dev.	Rel. error %
Hg + Mg	50.0 + 50.0	50.11	0.05	+0.22
Hg + Sn	15.0 + 85.0	14.95	0.03	-0.33
Hg + Na	67.7 + 32.3	67.79	0.04	+0.13

*Average of three determinations.

Conclusions: Masking agent 4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole does not form a precipitate with either the metal ion to be determined or the titrant. This facilitates sharp end-point. The proposed method has been compared with the earlier procedures. The method works well in the range 2–74 mg of Hg^{II} and requires no heating or cooling before the titration and does not require standardisation of EDTA. The method may be suitable for the determination mercury in its alloys.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

A 0.01 M mercuric nitrate and a 0.02 M zinc sulphate

solutions were standardized¹³. EDTA solution (~0.02 M) was prepared in distilled water. Xylenol orange was prepared by grinding of the indicator (1.0 g) with potassium nitrate (100 g). A 1% alcoholic solution of 4-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole was used¹⁴.

Procedure : To an aliquot of acidic solution containing 1–75 mg of Hg^{II}, a 0.02 M EDTA solution (1–20 ml) was added and diluted to 50–60 ml. Xylenol orange indicator (0.03 g) was added to it and the pH adjusted to 5.0–6.0 using hexamine (10–12 g). The excess of EDTA was then titrated against zinc sulphate solution. To it a 1% 4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole solution (10.5–23.0 ml) was added, mixed well and the liberated EDTA was titrated with zinc sulphate solution. This second titre value corresponded to the Hg^{II} present.

References

1. J. Korbl and R. Pribil, *Chem. Listy*, 1957, **51**, 667.
2. R. P. Singh, *Talanta*, 1969, **16**, 1447.
3. C. S. Vasilikiotis and C. D. Apostolopoulou, *Microchem. J.*, 1975, **20**, 66.
4. K. Ueno, *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, **29**, 1669.
5. H. R. A. Gadiyar, R. V. Gadag and M. R. Gajendragad, *Talanta*, 1982, **29**, 941.
6. B. Narayana and M. R. Gajendragad, *Talanta*, 1989, **35**, 719.
7. B. Narayana, G. T. Kuchinad and M. R. Gajendragad, *Chin. J. Chem.*, 1992, **10**, 394.
8. K. N. Raoot, S. Raoot and L. Kumari, *Talanta*, 1983, **30**, 611.
9. B. Mathew, B. M. Rao and B. Narayana, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1995, **118**, 197.
10. B. Mathew, B. Narayana and B. M. Rao, *Analyst*, 1995, **120**, 1097.
11. B. M. Rao and B. Narayana, *Chim. Acta Turc.*, 1993, **21**, 27.
12. B. M. Rao and B. Narayana, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1993, **111**, 251.
13. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", ELBS, London, 1951, 1978.
14. K. S. Dhaka, J. Mohan, V. K. Chadha and H. K. Pujar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 288.